

DE-RISK

Local Flexibility Markets (LFMs): Unlocking Value for Professionals

How DE-RISK empowers safe RES
integration, new services, and
consumer engagement

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Why LFMs Matter for Professionals?

Europe's energy system is rapidly decarbonizing. As renewables grow, grid stability becomes more complex. Local Flexibility Markets (LFMs) are a key solution:

- » **For DSOs:** reduce congestion, defer costly grid reinforcements, and increase hosting capacity for renewables.
- » **For aggregators:** new business models based on demand response.
- » **For installers & ESCOs:** value-added services for customers (smart controls, energy savings).
- » **For facility managers & cooperatives:** better energy cost management and transparency.

LFMs turn consumers into active participants in the energy transition while creating more space for local renewable energy.

DE-RISK Solutions at a Glance

The DE-RISK project demonstrates how LFMs can work in practice across 4 pilots (Spain, Türkiye, Ireland):

- » **QUE's Flexibility Platform**
 - ◇ Optimizes load shifting, HVAC/DHW control, and demand response.

Optimization Report for USER_12

Period: Jul 27 – Aug 03, 2025

Summary

We identified 3.9 kWh of consumption outside peak solar production hours.

This consumption primarily occurs between 8am to 8am, when solar production is minimal/non-existent.

Recommendation

Shifting this consumption to daytime hours (on average, 5.4 hours earlier) would improve your solar energy utilization.

Potential Benefits

Increased self-consumption
+1.0 kWh (+9.7%)

Reduced grid imports
-1.0 kWh (-5.1%)

Improved self-sufficiency
+3.3%

Economic Benefits

Cost savings
0.38 EUR (-13.2%)

Average energy price
0.1321 EUR/kWh

Original cost+Optimized cost
+1.0 kWh (+9.7%)

Visualization

Next Steps

Review detailed visualizations in the “output” directory for more insights into how specific loads could be shifted.

- » **R2M's WebApp**
 - ◇ User-friendly dashboards that increase awareness, show savings, and foster trust.
- » **DR Services**
 - ◇ Practical implementation of residential demand response, aligned with DSO signals (via an aggregator).

Enabling Equipment

- Smart meters and sensors
- HVAC & DHW controllers
- Rooftop PV

What We Learned in the Pilots*

Joven Futura (Murcia-Spain)

Existing IoT allowed fast deployment. Households valued transparency via the WebApp.

The Joven Futura pilot involves 18 multi-family apartments equipped with collective PV installations and dynamic tariffs. All homes rely exclusively on electricity for heating, cooling, and domestic hot water, making them ideal for demand response. Existing monitoring infrastructure was restored and expanded with new sensing and control equipment, integrated into QUE's Building Information Management Layer. The flexibility platform dispatches signals to HVAC and DHW systems, following aggregator signals, shifting consumption during peak periods without compromising comfort. Households access a web application to track their usage and savings, increasing engagement and trust.

La Balma (Barcelona-Spain)

Personalized weekly feedback boosted awareness, even with limited PV in winter.

La Balma is a cooperative housing project with 20 energy-efficient dwellings, a centralized geothermal heating system, and shared PV and storage. Here the focus was on **advice-driven engagement** rather than automated control. Each week, households received personalized messages showing their solar coverage, consumption, and tailored optimization tips. This low-cost, communication-centered approach raised awareness and fostered behavioral change, encouraging residents to align appliance use with PV production hours. While PV output was modest during winter simulations, demonstrations later showed higher self-consumption gains as solar generation increased.

*Results are based on simulated DSO signals and assumed TOU tariffs for the Turkish Pilot

Kepez (Çanakkale-Türkiye)

Retrofitting IoT in homes without prior infrastructure is feasible, delivering up to 17% bill savings.

In Kepez, 18 households were equipped with smart meters, sensors and controllers for HVAC and hot water systems, starting from a situation with no IoT infrastructure. The DE-RISK platform enabled remote control of loads and participation in simulated local flexibility services.

Without PV on site, the pilot tested tariff-based demand response by shifting consumption away from peak hours defined in segmented price bands. Demonstrations confirmed significant savings, with households achieving up to 17% lower electricity consumption during demand response events. The observed flexibility potential was 14.3 kWh, with 7.98 kWh activated in practice. The pilot proved that even in regions without dynamic tariffs or pre-existing IoT systems, tailored solutions can unlock meaningful flexibility and economic benefits.

Galway (NUIG-Ireland)

This 2,426 m² campus building served as a testbed for non-domestic building flexibility. A mix of single-use offices, labs, and lecture halls, was retrofitted with an Air Source Heat Pump and PV panels. DE-RISK deployed a LORA-controlled network of smart thermostatic radiator valves (TRVs) and occupancy-temperature-RH sensors across 40 rooms. A secure IoT architecture was developed with strong cybersecurity safeguards. The pilot tested occupancy-based heating controls, where unused rooms automatically reduced setpoints while maintaining comfort. Commissioning challenges revealed the complexity of integrating smart TRVs. Once operational, the system demonstrated its potential to shift up to 25–50% of the building's thermal load unlocking approx. 65kW Heat Pump electrical demand for up to two hours. The pilot highlights the opportunities and governance challenges of bringing demand response into large institutional settings.

Engaging Consumers: Tips for Professionals

Successful consumer engagement requires:

Trust & Transparency

Explain clearly what happens to their data and devices.

Comfort First

Ensure flexibility actions don't compromise daily life.

Financial Incentives

Aggregator payments motivate participation.

Simple Communication

Weekly messages or dashboards work better than technical reports.

Call to Action

LFMs can be scaled. Professionals can now:

- » Partner with DSOs and aggregators to deliver flexibility.
- » Use DE-RISK tools (flexibility platform + WebApp) to optimize and engage.
- » Replicate lessons learned from pilots across Europe.

Visit www.deriskproject.eu for resources, training materials, and tutorials.

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